

EC TiO₂ Food Ban

Commission regulation (EU) 2022/63, 14th Jan. 2022

Role play, Nanotraining School Venice, 2022-05-20

E171 in a nutshell

- Titanium dioxide is the naturally occurring oxide of titanium with a wide range of applications, from paint, sunscreen to food coloring and drug matrix and coating.
- E 171: Food additive titanium dioxide
- Less than 50% of particles in E 171 are smaller than 100 nm
- 1 % are smaller than 30 nm
- No daily uptake limit recommendation
- Total ban starting Feb. 2022

Result of the regulation process

Titanium dioxide: E171 no longer considered safe when used as a food additive

Published: 6 May 2021

Contents

- FAQ – EFSA 2021 safety assessment of titanium dioxide (E171)
- How to contact us
- Related topic(s)

<https://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/news/titanium-dioxide-e171-no-longer-considered-safe-when-used-food-additive>

EFSA has updated its safety assessment of the food additive titanium dioxide (E 171), following a request by the European Commission in March 2020.

No harmonized CLP Classification for TiO₂

Hazard classification	Hazard statement	Nr. of submitters
Not classified		2387
Acute Tox 4 – H332	Harmful if inhaled	63
Acute Tox 4 H312	Harmful in contact with skin	4
Acute Tox 4 H302	Harmful if swallowed	14
Skin Irrit 2 – H315	Causes skin irritation	11
Eye Irrit 2 – H319	Causes serious eye irritation	71
STOT SE 2 – H371	May cause damage to organs	10
Resp Sens 1 – H334	May cause allergy or asthma symptoms or breathing difficulties if inhaled	1
STOT SE 3 – H335	May cause respiratory irritation	76
STOT SE 1 – H372	Cause damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure	69
STOT SE 2 – H373	May cause damage to organs through prolonged or repeated exposure	1
Muta 2 – H341	Suspected of causing genetic effects	1
Carc 1B – 350	May cause cancer	9
Carc 2 – H351	Suspected of causing cancer	115
Aqua Chronic 4 – H413	May cause long lasting harmful effects to aquatic life	22

TiO₂ classification and food ban

ANSES
submits
Proposal for
Harmonized
Classification
and Labelling
May 2016

Comments
submitted to
ECHA during
public
consultation
(45 days)
July and
August 2016

ECHA's RAC
committee
submits
opinion
9 June
2017

CARACAL
meetings:
comments
by MSs
November
2017
March
2018

Additional
public
consultation
ECHA
closed on
8th Feb
2019

CARACAL
meetings
followed
June 2018
2019

Final CLP
decision
made by EC
February
2020

Food ban
imposed by
EC
May 2021

Results of different studies

- Intravenous and oral administration:
 - Cross placenta, long half lives, accumulation potential
 - Identified in liver and spleen
- No general organ toxicity
- Developmental toxicity → was not pursued further
- Genotoxicity → TiO₂ particles have a potential...
 - ... to break DNA strands
 - ... but no mutagenicity, no carcinogenicity
- Inflammation and immunotoxicity
 - Impairment of immune homeostasis (50 mg E171/bw per day)
- Aberrant crypt foci
 - Development of ACF in male rats (10 mg/bw per day)

Panel work

120 – 150 words statement, consensually agreed upon by all four stakeholder groups

- Background
- Strength of the evidence
- Definition of concern
- Recommendation for EC decision

EC TiO₂ Food Ban

Thank you for your interest

